

Bringing together African and European partners to fight skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa through an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline health workers.

SkincAlr holds its quarterly consortium meeting

SkincAlr Quarterly consortium meeting

On 9 October, the **SkincAlr consortium** held its quarterly coordination meeting online, bringing all partners together to review project progress and plan next steps. Led by the **Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)**, the session provided a valuable opportunity to share updates, address challenges, and strengthen collaboration as the project moves forward.

[Read the full article](#)

From vision to action: the SkincAlr origins story

In this series of interviews, we **explore SincAlr's journey from concept to reality**. We also hear from some of the people involved in the project about their vision for achieving our goal over the next five years: bringing together African and European partners to combat neglected tropical skin diseases in sub-Saharan Africa using an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline healthcare workers.

Carla Rodríguez, from Sherwood

In this interview, **Carla Rodríguez Cuesta**, operations coordinator at **Sherwood Science**, tells us how the idea for the project came about and what she hopes the future holds for SkincAlr.

“I would like to see SkincAlr operating in at least ten countries. We are going to make a big effort to talk to several health ministers and show them the validation study for SkincAlr, so that it can be integrated into their clinical workflow and health system”.

David Shaikh, from Sherwood

In this interview, **David Shaik**, CEO and Co-funder at **Sherwood Science**, tells us how the idea for the project came about and what he hopes the future holds for SkincAlr.

“In five years, **SkincAlr will be the go-to app for skin NTDs**. And hopefully, it will even become the WHO’s skin NTDs app”.

SkincAlr according to us

In this series, we meet some of the people behind SkincAlr and discover what makes the project so special from the partners' perspective.

Patrick de Marie Katoto, UCB

We present **Patrick de Marie Katoto**, associate professor of Medicine, Epidemiology and Global Health at the Université Catholique de Bukavu.

“SkincAir will be a game-changer. First, we will have capacity building, and then we will come up with an App to help us diagnose the disease. If we can achieve this, this will actually decrease the cost for patients and the health system. Secondly, not only the cost but actually the primary goal here is to **decrease the time taken for diagnosis.** If we decrease the time taken for diagnosis, we will also decrease the severity and improve the care for our people.”

María Pretel Aguilar, TeaCup Lab

We present **María Pretel Aguilar**, UX researcher at [TeaCup Lab](#).

“It is a project that could **help front-line health workers** detect skin NTDs more easily and help patients get treatment faster. Hopefully, we will see an increase in public health in general across sub-Saharan Africa”.

Tahir Dahiru, LTR

We present **Tahir Dahiru**, medical doctor by training and Executive Director at [Leprosy and TB Relief Nigeria - LTR](#).

“it's a very good project. A very good one in the sense that **it involves people from Europe and people from Africa**. We have local people in Africa who understand the terrain, have experience in field work and know how to work with

frontline healthcare workers and dermatologists. This mixture is going to give very good results, and I'm very optimistic about that.”

Kassa Haile, AHRI

We present **Kassa Haile**, local lead researcher at [Armaeur Hansen Research Institute - AHRI](#).

“At SkincAIr, we are a team of people from different countries with different expertise. I think this **could be exploited for other kinds of collaboration**. For example, I am a healthcare professional and a researcher, I could collaborate with IT and AI experts to improve the healthcare system.”

We present **Joanne Yego**, Research scientist at [Kenya Medical REsearch Institute - KEMRI](#).

“We have a team of people from different fields who are going to work together to improve the diagnosis of neglected tropical skin diseases. I hope that, by doing this, we will be able to achieve even more, and that **this app can be used all over the world** for diagnosing these diseases.”

SkincAlr Deliverables

D2.1 Completion of eCRF

Deliverable 2.1 presents the two electronic Case Report Forms (FWH eCRF and Dermatologist Dataset eCRF) used by SkincAlr to collect all clinical, epidemiological, and imaging data in a standardised and ethically compliant way. Implemented in the SkincAlr Research mobile app, both eCRFs support offline capture, end-to-end pseudonymisation, privacy-preserving geolocation (5–10 km grids), and secure synchronisation with full audit trails. The FWH eCRF underpins the two-year validation study (M12–M36), enabling measurement of early detection, diagnostic accuracy, diagnostic delay, surveillance indicators, knowledge retention, and micro-costing. The Dermatologist Dataset eCRF supports dataset creation (M12–M48) through structured metadata and high-quality image capture for AI development. Together, these instruments ensure robust KPI measurement, participant privacy, and high-quality data collection across all study countries.

[Read the deliverable](#)

SkincAir

DELIVERABLE

D6.1 DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN

published

D6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication plan

This deliverable presents the SkincAir project's integrated strategy for dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement, setting out tailored actions to maximise the project's reach and visibility from the outset. It defines the tools, channels, and activities that will be deployed to inform, inspire, and involve our target audiences, while fostering a strong community around the project's mission of advancing AI-driven solutions for early detection and management of skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa. The document also captures the initial promotional efforts and visual identity elements created to support our outreach activities— including the project's branding toolkit, online presence, participation in key events, and planned publications— laying the groundwork for impactful engagement throughout the project's lifecycle.

[Read the deliverable](#)

HAPPY NEW YEAR

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IN 2026, WE WILL BE WORKING HARD TO DEVELOP OUR SKINCAIR AI-DRIVEN MOBILE APPLICATION FOR DETECTING AND PREDICTING SKIN NEGLECTED TROPICAL DISEASES (NTDS).

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SkincAir Project

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